

ON THE QUESTION OF THE PRAGMATIC ASPECT OF TRANSLATING MEDIA HEADLINES

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Abstract. *The modern information society is inseparable from the mass media. Of particular interest is the translation of media headlines, since the title occupies a special place in the text – it firstly grabs audience attention, it helps to judge the content of the article, and also form some kind of preliminary attitude to the problem reflected in the text. The headline is able to make an emotional impact on the reader, which is especially important for the media. Therefore, the translator needs to take into account the characteristics of the target audience, which may differ from the characteristics of the target audience to which the original text was addressed. Concerning these differences, the translator can resort to a pragmatic adaptation of the text.*

The novelty of this study is that the theme of pragmatic adaptation is one of the most complex and least developed aspects of translation theory, as well as the growing interest in the problem, because the choice of one or another translation option should not be purely intuitive.

Keywords: *title, pragmatic aspect, linguistic analysis, translation, text adaptation, journalistic article.*

Introduction.

Pragmatic adaptation in translation is one of the problems of translation theory, among which there is also the problem of transmitting the pragmatic meanings of the original words and interpreting the pragmatic aspect of translation as the task of a specific act of translation.

Pragmatics, being one of the branches of linguistics, studies issues related to the varying degrees of understanding by the participants of the communicative process of certain linguistic units and speech works and with their different interpretation depending on the linguistic and non-linguistic (extralinguistic) experience of the participants of the communicative act.

In our study, we consider pragmatic adaptations in translating English-language media headlines into Russian. The first element of the article is the title by which we judge its content and decide whether it is worth reading. Along with the information, the title carries an emotional coloring that can arouse the reader's interest. According to a study conducted by psychologists, about 80% of readers pay their attention only to the headlines. Hence, the title is of great importance for journalistic articles, which is difficult to underestimate. A few words do not only reflect the content of the whole article, but also inspire the reader. However, journalists perceive these goals differently and show different results after all. Commonly, sensational and catchy headlines are worthless. This can lead to the fact that the reader will lose confidence not only in an individual article, but also in the publication as a whole. Therefore, it is not worth risking readers' trust for the sake of a momentary sensation. The headline represents the face of the entire newspaper, it affects the popularity of the publication.

Materials and methods.

The material for this study was the headline of various foreign publications, magazines and newspapers (The Washington Post, The Wall Street Journal, The Guardian, TheProjectSyndicate, etc.) presented on the Internet portal inosmi.ru. The methodological basis was the work of: Komissarov V.N., Retsker Ya.I., Schweitzer A.D., Neubert A., Barkhudarov L.S., Galperina I.R.

Firstly, we will look into the definitions of the concept of "title". V.I. Dahl in his dictionary defines the title as "the output sheet, the first sheet of a book or essay, where its name is indicated" [Dahl 2009]. In addition, the title can indicate the name of the department, the chapter of the book,

and in business papers, the value at the beginning of the department sheet, the place from where and where the paper goes. This is a broad concept of a header.

In the dictionary, S.I. Ozhegov has a narrower definition – as the name of a work (literary, musical) or a department of its parts [Ozhegov 2014].

These definitions remain true for the news headline, as it is part of the general concept of "title". However, the newspaper headline has its own peculiarities. He lives on the newspaper page, and therefore acquires the distinctive features of the newspaper. Many newspaper headlines convey the essence of the events in a concise and concise form. The main source for headlines is life itself, from which one should choose the brightest, and then it is interesting to present [Galperin 2005:15].

To achieve this goal, any of the existing lexical and syntactic means of expression can be used in the title. As a result, you can get expressive headlines created using the figurative meaning of words, colored vocabulary, synonyms and antonyms. Proverbs, sayings, phraseological units, names of famous songs, films, plays, famous quotes, colloquial elements, phonetic and morphological means of expression can give expressiveness and attractiveness to the title [Komissarov 1999:74].

Thus, the study of the structure of the title is inextricably linked with the study of other linguistic disciplines, namely syntax, morphology, lexicology, phonetics and phraseology, as well as stylistics.

The formation and development of functional stylistics as an independent scientific discipline was primarily associated with the search for extralinguistic conditions that determined the principles of selection and features of the functioning of language tools in various spheres of communication. This is confirmed throughout the history of the study of functional styles, including the language of newspapers. A well-known controversy of the 20s about the language of the press and ways to improve it showed the correctness of Prof. G.O. Vinokur, who connected the stylistic specificity of media texts with the conditions that generate it. The newspaper language inevitably acquired mechanized and automated features due to the exceptional rate of production designed for mass consumption. Ready-made templates, speech stamps and language cliches are used when constructing familiar newspaper statements (editorial, telegram, interview) [Vinokur 2001:48].

As a conclusion, G.O. Vinokur summed up: "There is almost not a single word in newspaper speech that would not be a stamp, a cliché, a template" [Vinokur 2001:49].

However, it was not conclusion of G.O. Vinokur, but the very attempt to provide an explanation of the quality of newspaper speech through style-forming factors, which today we call extralinguistic. Vinokur was the first who outlined the way to build a model of newspaper language, which was later presented by Prof. V.G. Kostomarov. According to the professor, this model "reveals itself as a mandatory and straight-line-constant correlation of standardized and expressive segments of the speech chain, by the action of orientations on expression and standard, constituting a single constructive principle" [Kostomarov 1999:85].

Results and discussions.

The term "pragmatic meaning" in modern linguistics is characterized by ambiguity. Thus, linguistics used the idea of three types of relations, which initially developed in the philosophical concepts of modern semiotics, characteristic of any sign. Such types of relations are also characteristic of signs of natural languages and are divided into: semantic, which determine the relationship between the signified object; syntactic, linking this sign with other signs of the same system; pragmatic, which reflect the connection of the sign and the persons using it in the communication process [Komissarov 1980].

According to Komissarov, linguistic signs can be distinguished by such meanings as: semantic (in other words, denotative or connotative), syntactic (or intra-linguistic) and pragmatic. In this case, it is customary to understand the word by a language sign. According to Komissarov, there is uncertainty in the relationship of this classification with other types of word meaning and

concepts of grammatical, lexical, denotative and connotative meanings of the word. Komissarov refers to the research of L. S. Barkhudarov, according to which the number of pragmatic meanings includes the stylistic characteristic of the word, its register (expressive characteristic) and emotional coloring, in other words, all the components of the semantics of the word, usually related to its connotation [Barkhudarov 1999:235].

When translating newspaper headlines, first of all, it should be noted that in the world of mass media, headlines are most often not translated – because publications acquire different language versions with their own headlines. Despite of the fact that a translator can receive an order to translate news articles along with headlines, and in this case, it is especially important to translate the original headline. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of the construction of headings in the original language and follow the usual norms and traditions of the target language. Below we will present some features of the construction of news headlines in English.

Spelling of headings. In most English-article headlines, each word is written with an uppercase (capital) letter, with the exception of articles and prepositions. However, this is not a universal rule, as some media and websites have left this practice in the past.

Grammatical and stylistic features of headlines. The most important grammatical feature of English-language news headlines is the specific ways of expressing the time of action. Their summary is given in Table 1.

Table 1 - Ways to indicate the time of action in news headlines in English.

Tense	The meaning of “I” in news	Examples
Future tense	participle I	Syria’s Humanitarian Situation Degenerating Fast
	nominal part of the predicate (without auxiliary verb)	Suspected Bubonic Plague Victims in Kyrgystan Healthy EU Foreign Policy Chief Hopeful on Iran Nuclear Talks Amur River Water Level in Flood-Hit Khabarovsk on Decline
	simple present tense (for non-terminal verbs)	Refugees Face Bleak Conditions in Underfunded Camps
Future Tense	Infinitive	Syrian Foreign Minister to Visit Moscow Next Week
Past tense (in active voice)	Present Simple tense	Belarus Raises Oil Export Duties China Vetoes US-Sponsored UN Resolution
Past tense (in the passive voice)	Participle II	Russia’s Discovery of New Element Verified Ivory Seized at Bangkok Airport

In turn, the style of English-language news headlines is characterized by conciseness, pithiness, and the desire to fit the maximum possible amount of information into a statement of minimal length. Initially, this principle was followed in newspapers and other printed publications based on the need to save space. Following this tradition, English-language media practice omitting the composition union in the title and replacing it with a comma:

Россия и Казахстан увеличили золотовалютные резервы
Russia and Kazakhstan increased gold reserves

Both Russian-speaking and English-speaking media are characterized by the ellipsis of the verb of speaking when pointing to the source of information:

Спикер Думы: экономическая политика США может сказаться на глобальном рынке

Duma Speaker: US Economic Policy May Impact Global Market

In addition to that the ellipsis of the verb of speaking is not mandatory. Even when using a verb, the following conjunction is usually omitted:

Япония заявила, что её экспортные морепродукты безопасны для потребления
Japan Says Fishery Exports Safe for Consumption

The use of articles. Another feature of news headlines is that the articles are omitted in most of them. This is demonstrated by the headings given above in the table; Here is another example:

Газпром и CNPC согласовали условия крупной сделки по газу, кроме ценовых
Gazprom, CNPC agree terms of big gas deal, except price

Highlighted nouns in an ordinary utterance would be used with articles (...the terms of a big gas deal, except the price). They are omitted in the news headline.

However, the article is not omitted if this may lead to a misunderstanding of the semantic or communicative structure of the title:

Марк Цукерберг: доступ в Интернет – одно из прав человек
Mark Zuckerberg: Web Access a Human Right

In this example, the indefinite article plays an important role: it conveys the meaning of 'one of' and, in addition, facilitates understanding the structure of the title, in which the verb-copula is omitted, denoting the nominal part of the predicate.

Lexical features. One of the features of the headings in AYA is the use of a special "heading" vocabulary – short (primarily monosyllabic) words that replace more "long" syllable ones. Such words were selected by newspaper practice primarily because of their brevity like omissions, allowed saving space on the newspaper page. Some of these lexical units are listed in table 2.

Table 2 - Some "header" units

быстро расти; быстрый рост	grow rapidly; rapid growth	boom
взрыв	explosion	blast
вызывать, быть причиной	cause, lead to, result in	spark
добиваться, требовать; стремиться к чему-либо	request, demand; make efforts to achieve	seek
договор, договорённость	treaty, agreement	pact
задерживать	detain	hold
заключать (сделку)	make, arrange, enter into (a deal)	clinch
запрещать; запрет	prohibit; prohibition	ban
катастрофа, авария	accident	crash
конфликт, спор	conflict, argument	clash row
критиковать	criticize	slam
наносить удар	strike	hit
наращивать; наращивание	step up, increase	boost
не допускать, исключать	deny access, exclude	bar

обдумывать, изучать возможность, присматриваться	consider	mull, eye
ограничивать, обуздывать; ограничение	(effort) to limit, to restrain	curb
переговоры, обсуждение	discussions; negotiations, talks	talks
поддерживать; поддержка	support	back
пожар, возгорание	fire	blaze
помогать; помощь	assist; assistance, aid	aid
попытка	attempt	bid
превышать	exceed	top
призывать	appeal for	urge
принимать решительные меры (против), обрушиваться (на)	take strong measures against	crack down on

This list of words is far from complete, and the use of "headline" vocabulary is not mandatory. However, knowing the special words and their use and meanings in translation is an indicator of the translator's high qualification. This skill is achieved by regularly reading reputable English-language media, studying the structure and lexical composition of news headlines.

Conclusions.

Grammatical features of English newspaper headlines and their transmission in translation:

1. Ellipsis

Full sentences in English-language news headlines are rare, and the structure of the headlines is often an ellipsis. Any parts of speech and sentence members can be omitted:

a) Omission of the subject

A significant difficulty is the translation of headings in which there is a verb predicate in the personal form, but there is no subject. When translating, such headings are transformed into vaguely personal sentences, and in some cases it becomes necessary to restore the subject, based on the text of the article:

Expect no change in North Korea

В Северной Корее изменений не ожидается

b) Omission of the predicate

The omission of the predicate is allowed if it plays a secondary role. Such headings are translated into Russian by name sentences:

WebProtest Протест в сети

Omitting the article attracts attention, makes the title more expressive.

The article is saved only when it is critical for understanding and correct interpretation of the message.

There is no analogue of the article omission in the Russian language, since for it the category of certainty/uncertainty is expressed within the framework of not grammatical, but lexical meaning.:

Vince Cable calls for mansion tax in next Budget

Винс Кейбл требует ввести в Англии налог на элитную недвижимость

(Omission of the article in this case makes the title more informative and dynamic)

d) Omission of the verb-copula to be in the passive

The verb-bundle to be is omitted in order to achieve greater informativeness and attract attention. There is no analogue to this phenomenon in the Russian language. The translator is faced with the task of seeing the passive in the original, without confusing it with other forms of the verb

235,000 Mini Coopers recalled over fire risk 235,000 Мини Куперов будет отозвано из-за опасности взрыва (опущение глагола-связки willbe)

Hundreds of lost Darwinian specimens discovered in cabinet *Найденны сотни потерянных экспонатов Чарльза Дарвина* (опущение глагола-связки were)

The English language is characterized by the widespread use of passive constructions. However, in Russian, the passive construction is not so frequent and stylistically neutral, so it is used much less often and replaced with an indefinite personal form:

At least two killed as three buildings collapse in Rio de Janeiro

В Рио-де-Жанейро обрушились три здания: погибли как минимум 2 человека

The headlines often use quotes expressed both directly and indirectly. The omission of the verb introducing the quote is used to save space. It also allows you to make the title more succinct and informative. In such cases, only the author's name and the quotation itself are indicated. Omission of the introducing verb is also acceptable in Russian. However, unlike English, where the link to the author can be at the beginning or at the end of the title, in Russian it is customary to put the link at the beginning, before the quote itself:

I'm too old for marriage: Oprah Winfrey

Опра Уинфрей: «Я слишком стара для замужества»

2. The tense forms of the verb

Significant differences from other functional styles of modern English are noted in the nature of the use of verb tenses in headings:

a) Events that occurred in the recent past are usually expressed in indefinite tense. [Bessonov 2009:239]

When translating, they are replaced by the past tense:

Pakistan blocks USenvoyvisit: official

Пакистан отказался принять американского дипломата

b) The future action, as a rule, is expressed through the infinitive:

Lloyds Banking Group to cut 700 jobs

Банковская группа LloydsBankingGroupсократит 700 с рабочих мест

Pragmatic relations are divided into 4 types, taking into account which pragmatic adaptation of the source text is made, i.e. making certain adjustments to socio-cultural, psychological and other discrepancies between the receptors of the original and translation texts. There are four types of pragmatic adaptation of the text. The purpose of the first type is to provide adequate understanding of the message by translation receptors. The purpose of the second one is to achieve the correct perception of the original content, to convey to the translation receptor the emotional impact of the source text. The third type of pragmatic adaptation is focused on a specific receptor and a specific communicative situation. The fourth type of pragmatic adaptation can be characterized as the solution of an "extra-translation super-task".

In the pragmatic adaptation of the text, the translator uses a variety of translation transformations – lexical, syntactic, stylistic.

Thus, the translator either tries to preserve the pragmatic potential of the original, or tries to ensure that this text has a different pragmatic potential, more or less independent of the pragmatics of the source text. Taking into account the peculiarities of a specific communicative situation, the translator chooses one or another pragmatic approach to his activity.

As a result of the study, the following conclusions were made:

1. Title – the initial element of the publication, its name. It has a double structure – it stands outside the text and is simultaneously connected with it.

2. The main task of the title is to attract readers' attention to the publication, and its three main functions are nominative, pragmatic and informative.

3. Headlines are divided into unidirectional and complex, full-informative and incomplete-informative.

4. English-language news headlines have their own characteristics that should be taken into account when translating: stylistic and grammatical features, special "headline" vocabulary, clichés. When translating English-language headings into Russian, the necessary grammatical, stylistic and lexical transformations are performed.

5. In order to preserve the pragmatic potential of the original text, the translator can and should make various changes to the translation text.

6. The translator should take into account that the linguistic means of the original, with the help of which the pragmatic potential of the original text was created, cannot simply be replaced in translation by the same type of linguistic means of the target language, because it will not be possible to adequately convey the pragmatic potential of the original text.

7. When transmitting the pragmatic potential of the original text, it is important not only to adequately convey the lexical meaning, but also the syntactic meaning and stylistic coloring of the original.

8. The translator should rely on the analysis of the context of the translated passage, that is, the text of the translation should have the same effect (emotional or aesthetic) on the reader of the translation that the original text has on the reader of the original.

With the analysis of the translations of the English-language headlines, we want to show that the translator needs to take into account the receiver in translating process who can be a Russian-speaking reader. Making certain adaptations in translation adaptations, which we stated above, ensure the reproduction of the same content as in the original, and also cause an equivalent intellectual and emotional reaction.

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